

Establish of Protocol for *Cucumis melo* L. Using Different Hormones Through Plant Tissue Culture Technique

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Abstract

Melon (*Cucumis melo* L.) is economically importance plants in agricultural production in the province of Balochistan, Pakistan. In this study, we developed various regeneration and transformation protocols and we examined the different earlier morphological characters of *Cucumis melo* on MS medium with different combinations and concentration of plant growth regulators (PGRs) (Auxin, cytokinin, and gibberellin). Result showed that the maximum value of callus was obtained when 0.50mg l^{-1} of BAP was combined with 0.50mg l^{-1} of 2,4-D about 52%. The maximum regeneration percentage was obtained by the combination of 1mg l^{-1} NAA, 0.5mg l^{-1} BAP and 0mg l^{-1} KIN about 80%. Although, the mean number of shoots were displayed a maximum value in MS medium having the combination of 2.5mg l^{-1} NAA, 1mg l^{-1} BAP, and 0mg l^{-1} KIN about 2.4 ± 0.3 . In addition, when the treatment was treated with 1.5mg l^{-1} BAP, and 0.5mg l^{-1} IBA showed a significant response on morphological parameters of studied plants. Similarly, the maximum number of roots, root and shoot length was observed when treated with 2mg l^{-1} of IAA and IBA respectively. We assume that statement of the research findings presented here lead to for further studies on in vitro propagation of melon plants.

Keywords: *Cucumis Melo* L, MS Medium, Regeneration, Callogenesis, Organogenesis.

Introduction

Vegetables are rich in vitamins and minerals as therefore the best source of human diet. They are helpful to fill the requirements of nutrition's. These are best naturally and can help us to keep healthy by protecting against disease. Various crops have different significance in the field of health, social, economic and biological. An annual trailing vine plant Cucumber

which is belonging to family *Cucurbitaceae*, one of the most abundant growing vegetables of the family after watermelon. Supply and demand of the cucumber vegetables has been widely enhanced in recent decades and it is growing among the world creates by the help of different fields such as greenhouse culture (Kadi *et al.*, 2018). Cucumber plant cultivated widely in which the number of chromosomes found, $2n = 14$. In India this plant considered as an endemic according to (De Candole, 1967). Commonly, this plant is monoecious, annual, trailing vine (or) climbing plant (Bailey, 1969).

Balochistan province is famous for the production of quality deciduous fruits like, almond, apple, apricot, grapes, cherry, peach, and plum, this is because of climate sustainability. *Cucumis* plants with various varieties are grown in the highland regions of the province such as, Quetta, Killa Abdullah, Pishin, Kalat, Mastung, Zhob and Lorlai districts. Agriculture sector development depends upon groundwater availability, that is extensively pumped out and as result decline the table of groundwater. The *Cucumis* plants have short duration of growing and contain a high amount of carbohydrates so that, it is good source of energy for human beings. Fruit is used in the form of both dried and in a fresh form known as Kishmish and Monaka.

Cucumis melo L, a melon vegetable crop, it is one of the most essential crops throughout the globe, especially in Asia. According to Sebastian *et al.*, (2010), this plant is grown in warm climates and in temperate region of the world. Compounds which are called carotenoids produced by the plants which are vital for plants and also for animals (Wong *et al.*, 2004). This vegetable crop is highly nutritious and one of the best source natural β -carotene (Vitamin A). Such essential carotenoids have importance for human health including β -carotene and α -carotene (Mares-Perlman *et al.*, 2002). Similarly, some carotenoids are known to prevent chronic diseases, these carotenoids are included lycopene and β -carotene (Sugiura *et al.*, 2008). In terms of genetics studies this plant has considered one of the attractive crops due to its biological features for the ripening of fruits as compared to other species of *Cucumis* (Pech *et al.*, 2008).

Plant regulators are hormone which are essential for the growth of plants when used in constant concentrations, species specify, stage of application, and seasons. Plant growth hormones play vital role to modify the physiology and morphology of the vegetations. PGRs effects the growth of plant such as its production and morphogenesis. It can be used in accurate concentrations, seasons, stage of application and species (Birader and Navalagatti, 2008). These are elaborate in different features in development and growth of plant such as

auxin and gibberellins. PGRs are organic substance which are usually applicable to change the growth of plant and used in low concentrations mostly for maintaining the natural growth regulatory system. The present study describes the several methods and characteristics in order to identify the effects of growth regulators (Auxin, cytokinin's and gibberellins) on growth of *Cucumis melo*, L.

Materials and Methods

Seeds Sowing and Plant Collection

The seeds of *Cucumis* plant were grown in the field at botanical garden in University of Balochistan, Quetta. After that, the seeds were growing completely, and became mature plants. Then, the new leaves and stem nodes of *Cucumis* plants were taken for the investigation of micropropagation.

The Culture Environment

The plants which are growing in a tissue culture lab, the needs for growing should be provided such as culture vessel, the growth medium as well as the external environment like light, and temperature. The medium of growth has contained all required essential mineral ions which necessary for development and growth. In addition, several other organic supplements like vitamins and amino acids are added in some cases. The culture of several plant cells, however it does not display any photosynthetic activities but needs carbon source which is provided in the form of sucrose. The main biological solvent water must be supplied in culture medium. Similarly, the physical factors like pH, temperature, osmotic pressure, light quality and duration, and the gaseous environment could be maintained within tolerable limits (Dahleen, 1999)

Media Preparation

The medium was supplemented with various growth regulators and other major salts were added in distilled water for callusing, shoot proliferation, and further regeneration of *Cucumis spp* (Murashige, and Skoog, 1962). The required amount of solution was taken for the preparation of medium. The carbohydrates source was added in the form of sugar (30 gl⁻¹), and the pH of medium was adjusted at 5.6, while the agar 8 gl⁻¹ was added as a source of solidifying agent. Then 10 ml amount of medium was taken in test tube which was covered by plastic sheet and kept into autoclave for 15 minutes at 121 °C under 1.5 kg/m² pressure before to culturing because to prevent for any fungal attack.

Media Sterilization

The media was sterilized at temperature 121°C and psi 15 for 20 minutes in autoclave. Then the media was kept in growth room controlled at temperature 25°C, and also provided the light intensity about 2500 lux. After that the shoots tips of explants were taken for invitro germination and used for further regeneration of the explant.

Plant Cell Culture Media

The culture media used for the cultivation of plant cells invitro medium and made of three basic components such as essential elements or mineral ions (supplies as a complex mixture of salts); organic supplement (providing vitamins and amino acids); fixed carbon (provided in the form of sugar sucrose).

Essential Elements

There are several components when combined to makes usually a complete medium of plant tissue culture (Street, 1977). Macro nutrients are beneficial to consider some of the individuals briefly for the stock solutions (Murashige and Skoog, 1962). A stock solution which implies for such elements needs in huge amount for the development and growth of plants. The elements included in this category are, carbon, phosphorus, nitrogen, calcium, magnesium, sulphur, and potassium. These are added separately and in the dry weight of plants these elements contain at least 0.1% generally (Murashige and Skoog, 1962). Micronutrients are including: manganese, cobalt, copper, boron, iron, zinc and molybdenum. In some formulation the elements other than these such as aluminium and nickel are found commonly (Murashige and Skoog, 1962). Iron in the form of iron sulphate is added usually and combination with iron sulphate ethylene diamine tetra acetic acid (EDTA) is utilized generally. EDTA form a complex with the iron and allows the continuous and slow release of iron into the medium (Street, 1977).

Organic Supplement

The culture of plant cells in vitro medium there are two vitamins such as myoinositol (vitamin B) and thiamine (vitamin B1) are measured and considered essential for the growth of crops (Street, 1977). In the organic supplement amino acids are also included commonly. Glycine is used most frequently and others are asparagine, aspartic acid, arginine, alanine, proline, glutamic acid and glutamine however in some cases its enrolment is not essential.

Similarly, casein hydrolysate amino acid used as a cheap source of amino acids in medium relatively (Street, 1977).

Carbon Source

Carbon source is form of sucrose which is easily available, readily assimilated, cheap, relatively stable therefore, it is often used carbon source generally. Other than sucrose; maltose, galactose, sorbitol and galactose carbohydrates can be used also (Szweykowska, 1974).

Gelling Agents

Gelling agents may be used in the form of solid (or) liquid which are depending upon the type of culture in vitro medium. It must be solidified for any types of culture which need the cells (or) tissue of plant to be grow in medium surface. Agar is one of the most common types of gelling agent which produced from seaweed and is ideal for routine applications (Szweykowska, 1974).

Plant Growth Regulators

Plant growth regulators (PGRs) are essential components of media that determines the way of development of plant cells. PGRs are used as plant hormones commonly (or) their synthetic analogues (Szweykowska, 1974).

Classes of Plant Growth Regulator

Auxins

Auxins are plant hormones that enhance the growth and division of cells. Indole acetic acid (IAA) is one of the most common natural occurring auxins. Similarly, the auxin 2,4-dichloro phenoxy acetic acid (2,4-D) and indole-3-butyric acid (IBA) used mostly and can extremely effective in most circumstances (Yeoman and Macleod, 1977).

Cytokines

Cytokinin's promote the division of cell. These occur naturally such as 2-isopentyl adenine (2iP) and zeatin which are beneficial in the culture of plant tissues. The synthetic analogues are used more frequently including kinetin and benzyl amino purine (BAP) (Yeoman and Macleod, 1977).

Gibberellins

Gibberellins are naturally occurring, numerous plant hormones, and structurally related compounds termed 'gibberellins (Knobloch, 1957). These hormones are regulating the elongation of cell and can agronomically important in determining fruit setting and height of plant. In plant tissue culture, only a few of gibberellins are used among these the most common being is gibberellic acid (GA₃) (Yeoman and Macleod, 1977).

Explant Preparation and Shoot Induction

The shoots of *Cucumis melo* were extracted after one month old from vitro developed tissue culture media aseptically. The leaves were cut from the shoot close to the intersection of the petiole and lamina. The recover components of plant leaf structure like petioles, leaflets, and even complete leaves were examined perfectly. The development controllers such as, 2 mg l⁻¹ BAP in blend with 0.1 mg l⁻¹ IBA in mix with 0.1 mg l⁻¹ NAA were utilized to recover the shoots from the complete sample (leaf with petiole). Leaves were injured abaxially through a surgical blade crosswise over the primary vein, and the side of adaxial was refined to touch the medium in all examination. After being refined, petri dishes were fixed with clean para film. The culture was grown under proper photoperiod (light and dim) at 28 ° C and it was checked daily form the contamination of any fungal or bacterial infections.

Multiplication of The Regenerated Shoots

After 4 weeks the recovered shoots were poured into a new medium in culture vessels, and it was adjusted gradually to light by the help of straightforward (glass) material. After that, when size of shoot reached to 10mm or more in height, they were again relocated to a medium of shoot reproduction, and allowed to grow at 270 ° C. The MS medium for shoot growth was comprised of 2 mg l⁻¹ BAP, and at that point, light adjusted recovered shoots were sub-cultured.

In Vitro Rooting of Shoots

The shots of *Cucumis melo* after 1 month were established on a full quality 20 ml of MS medium supplemented with 3% of sucrose, and at different amounts of IBA and IAA. After 30 days upon each treatment of IBA and IAA, the following parameters like length, quantity of primary roots, and shots length were recorded respectively. At 270 ° C the shoots were maintained regularly.

Acclimatization

From the culture vessels, the sprouts shoot and root were removed, and the roots were washed with tap water to remove the sucrose and agar. Then, the sprouts were poured to a bag of plastic (12cm in diameter), and containing sterilized soil, sand, and compost (cow-dung) at a ratio of 1:2:1, respectively. The sprouts were sheltered with the clear plastic bag to preserve moisture and were sprinkled at one-day intervals. The plastic cover was slowly removed after the sprouts were successfully established in an insect-proof glasshouse for one month.

Experimental Design, Data Collection and Analyses

The study was arranged as complete randomized design (CRD). A total of 6 explants per jar were used for all experiments with shoot initiations. 5 replicates were used for each experiment of culture per jar, and which was set as the experimental unit for leaf explant. The data of shoot as well as multifaction of shoot, number, and length of rooted plantlets, and also their survival rate in the glasshouse were analysed statistically by the help of one-way examination of variance (ANVOA).

Result and Discussion

Effects of BAP and 2,4-D Various Combinations on Callus Induction of *Cucumis Melo*

The callus induction of *Cucumis melo* was showed different value on the various combination of BAP and 2,4-D hormones. However, among 5 various combinations of BAP and 2,4-D treatments, the best and maximum value of callus was obtained when 0.50 mg l⁻¹ of BAP was combined with 0.50 mg l⁻¹ of 2,4-D (52%) (table 4.1). Although, the other 4 combinations displayed a various result, however these were not showing a great result in terms of callus induction of *Cucumis melo* (table 4.1). Hanana *et al.*, (2002) reported that the combination of 1mg l⁻¹ of BAP and 0.5mg l⁻¹ was efficient to induce the caulogenesis, and somatic embryogenesis in melo calli. In our study, we observed that the high amount of plant growth regulators in the MS medium reduced the callus induction. Similar result has also been reported by Debeaujon and Branchard, (1993) in melon plants.

Table 1: Hormone Response Using MS Media

Name of media	BAP/2,4-D conc. mg l ⁻¹	% of callus induction	Proliferation
MS	0	0	-
MS	0.25 0.25	18	+

MS	0.50 0.50	52	+++
MS	0.75 0.75	32	++
MS	0.1 0.1	18	+

Poor=+; Fair=++; Good=+++

Effects of NAA, BAP and on Regeneration %, Callus Induction % and Number of Shoots of *Cucumis melo*

Different concentration of 3 types of hormones were investigated on 3 different parameters of *Cucumis melo*. Overall, 12 treatments were prepared by the combination of 3 types of growth regulators. The maximum regeneration percentage was obtained by the combination of 1mg l^{-1} NAA, 0.5mg l^{-1} BAP and 0mg l^{-1} KIN about 80%. Similarly, the maximal percentage of callus (38%) was obtained in MS medium added with NAA 2.5mg l^{-1} , BAP 1mg l^{-1} , and KIN 0mg l^{-1} . However, overall, the callus induction in all tested amounts of growth regulators was positively low. Although, the mean number of shoots were displayed a maximum value in MS medium having the combination of 2.5mg l^{-1} NAA, 1mg l^{-1} BAP, and 0mg l^{-1} KIN about 2.4 ± 0.3 . However, the growth regulators combinations including KIN did not perform very well in all 3 investigated parameters in low tested levels (table 4.2). Both calli and no of shoots were reduced in treatments of 3mg l^{-1} of NAA, and in lower concentrations of BAP, and KIN simultaneously (table 4.2). In our study, the MS medium containing 2.5mg l^{-1} NAA showed that supplying NAA in the medium increased the callus formation, however the BAP and KIN amounts was the similar to that of previous study (Dirks and Buggenum, 1989). The main difference in the present study and previous study are growth regulators, and selected of melon cultivars. Tekdel and Cetiner, (2013) reported the shoots regenerations in two cultivars of Turkish melon varieties (Hasanbey, Cinikiz) which exhibited the maximum shoots regenerations percentage in MS medium supplemented with 2mg l^{-1} NAA, 1mg l^{-1} BAP, 0.5mg l^{-1} KIN that is showed similarities with result of present works. According to Chee, (1992) the maturation of somatic embryos could be affected on MS medium containing NAA and KIN or gibberellins (Tabei *et al.*, 1991).

Table 2: Effects of Growth Regulator Combinations on Regeneration %, Callus Induction %, and no. of Shoots.

Growth regulator conc. mg l^{-1}			Variables (<i>Cucumis melo</i>)		
NAA	BAP	KIN	Regeneration %	Callus induction %	Mean no of shoots
0	0	0	0.0	0.0	0 ± 0.0
0	0.5	0.5	0.0	0.0	0 ± 0.0
1.5	0.5	0	0.0	14	0 ± 0.0
1	0.1	0	3.5	0.0	1.6 ± 0.8

2.5	1	0	6	38	1.2±0.6
1	0.5	0	80	0.0	2.4±0.3
0.28	0.23	1.5	0.0	0.0	0±0.0
2	0.1	0	7.2	0.0	0.9±0.1
2	0.5	0	0.0	22	0±0.0
3	0.1	0	2.3	0.0	1±0.0
3	0.5	1	0.0	0.0	0±0.0
3	1	0	0.0	0.0	0±0.0

The data represent the regeneration rate and mean number of shoots per explant ± standard error of the experiments.

Effects of BAP, and IBA Regeneration %, Callus Induction and Number of Shoots of *Cucumis melo*

The combination of BAP, and IBA showed a great difference on the *Cucumis melo* plants. However, their various combined value concentration on lower, and higher concentrations did not perform a significant result, however in suitable combined range value showed a positive response on *Cucumis melo* plants. From the 12 tested levels of treatments maximum value of regenerations was observed when the treatment was treated with 2mg⁻¹ BAP, and 0.1 mg⁻¹ IBA about 83%. Similarly, the best 38% of callus induction was observed when the treatment was treated with 1.5mg⁻¹ BAP, and 0.5mg⁻¹ IBA. In addition, the maximum mean number of shoots were obtained in treatment which was treated with 2mg⁻¹ BAP, and 0.1mg⁻¹ IBA about 2.3 ±0.6 (table 4.3). Hanana *et al.*, (2002) described that the treatment supplemented with 1mg⁻¹ BAP and 0.5mg⁻¹ IBA showed a maximum regeneration percentage, and callus induction percentage on *Cucumis melo* plants. These findings are similar to that present result of *Cucumis melo* plants. According to Probowati and Daryono, (2018) stated that for callus induction of melon plants on MS medium is optimally obtained with addition of IBA 2mg⁻¹, and 1mg⁻¹ BAP.

Effects of growth regulator combinations on regeneration %, callus induction %, and no.

Table 3: Effects of growth regulator combinations on regeneration %, callus induction %, and no. of shoots of *Cucumis melo*.

Growth regulator conc. mg ⁻¹		Variables (<i>Cucumis melo</i>)		
BAP	IBA	Regeneration %	Callus induction %	Mean no of shoots
0	0	0.0	0.0	0±0.0
0.1	0.5	0.0	0.0	0±0.0
0.5	0.5	0.0	0.0	0±0.0
1	0.5	0.0	0.0	0±0.0
1.5	0.1	0.0	18	0± 0.0
1.5	0.5	0.0	38	0±0.0

2	1	9	26	1.9±0.1
2	0.1	83	0.0	2.3±0.6
2	0.5	5.1	8	1.8±0.1
3	1	0.0	0.0	0±0.0
3	0.1	3.9	0.0	0.8±0.9
3	0.5	0.0	0.0	0±0.0

The data represent the regeneration rate and mean number of shoots per explant $\pm$ standard error of the experiments.

Effects of IAA, and IBA on Number of Roots, Root and Shoot Length

The well-established plantlets were transferred to a MS medium treated with IAA, and IBA regulators. Overall, 5 treatments were prepared for each regulator. In IAA treatments, the maximum number of roots, root, and shoot length were observed in a MS medium of 2mg l^{-1} (4.45 ± 0.56 , 4.34 ± 0.12 , 3.9 ± 0.19), and followed by 1mg l^{-1} (3.1 ± 0.34 , 3.42 ± 0.9 , 2.86 ± 0.23). Similarly, in case of IBA, the maximum and best result of number of roots, root and shoot length was observed in treatment of 2mg l^{-1} about (5.63 ± 0.1 , 4.9 ± 0.45 , 7.5 ± 0.88), and followed by 1mg l^{-1} (4.34 ± 0.1 , 3.56 ± 0.58 , 6.6 ± 1.0) (table 4.4). For both plant regulators, the lowest and highest levels of tested treatments showed a lowest mean value of studied parameters of *Cucumis melo* (table 4.4). Thus, the growth regulators had a great positive influenced on the root, and shoot growth of *Cucumis melo*. According to Neumann *et al.*, (2009) the hormones such as IAA, and IBA most labile hormone to temperature and most rapidly experiencing to photooxidation. Although some melon cell structure state the use of IAA as one component of growth regulator substances can regenerate callus into plantlet. From this study we concluded that the use of IAA can differentiate callus into root. Moreno *et al.*, (1985) reported that within the range of IAA and IBA stimulated the root and shoot length of melon plants.

Table 4: Effects of growth regulators on no. of roots, root, and shoot length of *Cucumis melo*.

Treatment	Variables (<i>Cucumis melo</i>)		
	No of roots	Root length	Shoot length
IAA mg l^{-1}			
0	2.9 ± 0.12	1.56 ± 0.12	0.86 ± 0.12
1	3.1 ± 0.34	3.42 ± 0.9	2.86 ± 0.23
2	4.45 ± 0.56	4.34 ± 0.12	3.9 ± 0.19
3	3.1 ± 0.23	3.25 ± 0.12	1.9 ± 0.66
4	2.75 ± 0.1	2.19 ± 1.0	1.6 ± 1.0
IBA mg l^{-1}			
0	1.9 ± 0.21	0.98 ± 0.13	4.5 ± 0.76
1	2.34 ± 0.02	1.89 ± 0.99	4.6 ± 0.89

2	5.63±0.1	4.9±0.45	7.5±0.88
3	4.34±0.1	3.56±0.58	6.6±1.0
4	3.23±0.08	2.8±0.33	2.8±0.19

The data represent the no. of roots, root and shoot length per explant ± standard error of the experiments.

Acclimatization

The vitro regenerated plantlets were adjusted under a controlled environment. After one month they became a completely healthy mature plants with 80% of survival rate.

Conclusion

Thus, the *Cucumis melo* was selected as research material for the study presented here due to its importance for the Balochistan, agricultural production. It is essential to know the growth of regulators in the development of selected *Cucumis melo* has highly facilitated melon production under controlled environment. On the base of obtained date we observed that the average concentrations of growth regulators beneficial for regeneration, callus induction, and number of shoots, however at lower and higher concentration these could not show any positive response on the production of melon plants. In addition, the resulting data can be also used for research on melon developmental of root and shoot length, an intensive continuation of in vitro propagation studies is essential as well. It is suggested further studies are needed to analyze the various other cultivars of melon in the province of Balochistan.

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